

FULL PAPER- PREDICTIVE MODEL AND ACCELERATED CHARACTERIZATION OF VISCOELASTIC RELAXATION IN BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS

J.X. Lv¹, Y. Xiao^{2*}

^{1,2} School of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University, Shanghai 20092,
China

(* E-mail: y_xiao@tongji.edu.cn)

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ABSTRACT

Preload loss in pretensioned bolts is an inevitable phenomenon and numerous causes for bolt relaxation exist. The study presented in this paper focuses in an investigation of temperature-time dependent behaviour for the viscoelastic preload relaxation and prediction method for its long-time performance experimentally and theoretically. A new preload prediction model was developed an accelerated experimental program was conducted to study its temperature dependence and extrapolate the long-term behaviour. A good agreement between the model prediction and the accelerated tests results identifies the present model's validity regarding bolted composite joints relaxation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite material currently have a wide variety of application in aircraft, automobiles, appliances, business equipment, medical instruments and recreation equipment. One important area of concern for the engineer, when considering the long-term aspects of structural design with composite materials, is the strength of mechanically fastened joints due to their relative simplicity and their undeniable benefit when it comes to ease of disassembly [1]. Some studies emphasize that preload relaxation significantly affected the joint strength [2-4]. Hart-Smith [5] reported that the preload was determined to have a direct effect on joint bearing strength, with a 3500 lbs clamp-up force increasing the joint strength as much as twenty-eight percent over that of a finger-tight joint. Sun et al. [6] demonstrated the importance of clamp-up force on bolt strength through finite element analysis and experimental validation. Starikov and Schon [7] worked on fatigue of laminated composite bolted joints loaded in-plane and demonstrated that the clamp-up forces can influence the fatigue life and also that the applied load influences the clamp-up force distribution as the connection deforms. The potential impact of preload loss in the connection would lead to catastrophic consequences. It is desired to develop a connection prediction methodology that includes the joint relaxation over time in the fastening bolts after the initial load has been applied [8-11].

Analysis of residual stress based on creep test results is a primary method to avoid the complexity of relaxation tests. Schimitt and Horn [12] and Horn and Schimitt [13] studied the relaxation process in bolted thermoplastic composite joints and observed that by increasing initial preload the joint bearing failure load increased by as much as 28%. Joint load relaxation was also monitored and 6–16% relaxation from the initial preload was observed for short duration (1400 h) and long duration (100,000 h), respectively. Caccese et al. [14] presented their work on preload relaxation in various types of joints with different combination of connection members, such as, composite-to-composite joint, composite-to-aluminum joint, aluminum-to-aluminum joint and composite-to-steel joint. They finally found that the member role of composite aggravated relaxation much more than other materials.

In terms of quantitatively characterizing preload relaxation in bolted joints, the method of modeling the creep behaviour of material has been widely used over the years for the reason that creep primarily gives rise to load relaxation phenomenon in bolted connections, wherein creep effects are typically observed in the through-thickness direction. Based on the assumption of time hardening, that is, assuming that only transient creep stage exists during the whole creep behavior, Shivakumar and Crews [16] developed a quantitative expression relating the non-dimensional preload loss versus time as called Shivakumar-Crews model (S-C model) which included the effects of temperature and

humidity. Taira [17] summarized numerous phenomenological models wherein Hook-Norton model (H-N model) was specially mentioned. H-N model was derived under the assumption of strain-hardening, that is, only steady creep stage was considered during the derivation. Both models lay a foundation of relaxation prediction and indeed explain some objective phenomenon. However, it is noteworthy that, these models are all derived under an assumption that the creep status doesn't change. But the truth is, the creep property of material is changeable with respect to time. Typical strain-time curves obtained from creep tests at constant load over sufficiently long periods of time often exhibit three characteristic stages, these are: primary or transient creep (Following the setting in of the instantaneous elastic strain, the material deforms rapidly but at a decreasing rate. the duration of this stage is typically short in relation to the total creep curve.), secondary or steady-state creep (Here, the creep strain rate reaches a minimum value and remains approximately constant over a relatively long period of time.) and tertiary creep (In this stage, the creep strain rate accelerates rapidly. This stage is usually neglected in terms of composites) (see, Figure 2 in Section 2.1). The validity and accuracy of those above models are limited largely because of the ignorance of the creep status changing, such as, S-C model ignores the secondary creep and H-N model ignores the primary creep.

In recent year, the accelerated testing methodology [15] has been used prevalingly based on the Time-Temperature Superposition Principle (TTSP) for composites. The TTSP provides a method by which long-term behaviour can be predicted from short-term tests. Central to the study of the TTSP is a concept of temperature shift factor which will be described later.

In this paper, efforts on relaxation of composites joints were made both theoretically and experimentally. A new model for preload relaxation in bolted joints was developed based on the total-strain theory, i.e., primary and secondary creep stages are both concerned in order to prevent the above mentioned deficiencies of phenomenological models. And, a relaxation testing program was developed to observe the time-dependent relaxation behaviour of bolted joints and extrapolate its long-term behaviour.

2 THEORETICAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Formulation of phenomenological model

The schematic diagram of force vs. deformation of bolted joints is illustrated in Figure 1 for a better understanding of the preload loss mechanisms induced by creep of joint members. O_B and O_J represent original length of bolt and thickness of connection respectively. As the structure is tightened due to the applied torque, the bolt and the joining components interact from each other and reach to an equilibrium position, O . The bolt elongates (δ_B^0) and the joining components compressed (δ_J^0). A tension force namely preload is produced (P_0) to resist this deformation. With time goes by, the viscoelastic creep of interconnection material intensifies the deformation. It decreases the stiffness of the joining components with the stiffness of bolt changeless. As a result, elongation of bolt reduces

Fig.1 Force-deformation diagram of bolted joints

to δ'_b and compression of joining components increases to δ'_j , whereas, the whole deformation Δ remains constant. Equilibrium position shifts from O to O_t , and accordingly residual clamping force decreases from P_0 to P_t . The illustrated schema therefore, presents that residual preload will decline due to the creep of interconnection materials. To take a step further, variation of the creep is quantitatively associated with the residual preload and based on what, the developed approach below provides an effective solution to the relaxation prediction of bolt preload in a joint from early awareness of relaxation at an embryo stage.

We denote that the creep of joining components can be evaluated by the sum of instantaneous strain ε_0 , transition creep (primary creep) strain $\beta\sigma^{n'}t^m$ and steady creep (secondary creep) strain $k\sigma^n t$ based on creep total strain theory, as shown in Figure 2, which can be described as follows

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon_0 + \beta\sigma^{n'}t^m + k\sigma^n t, \quad (1)$$

where β, k are coefficients related to material property and temperature, n', n and m are indicative

Fig.2 Creep strain/rate vs time

of material property. The transient component is proportional to t^m , while the steady component is to t .

The creep rate $\dot{\varepsilon}_c$, the first derivative of creep ε_c with respect to time is depicted by

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c = m\beta\sigma^{n'}t^{m-1} + k\sigma^n. \quad (2)$$

As the creep initiates, the primary creep $m\beta\sigma^{n'}t^{m-1}$ decreases with time and dominates the whole polynomial because the value of m is less than 1. When t gets larger, the secondary creep $k\sigma^n$ turns to dominate the polynomial and the creep rate tends to be constant. Provided that t^* is the critical time while the transition creep transforms into steady creep, the creep rate formula then is formed in segmentally:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c = \begin{cases} m\beta\sigma^{n'}t^{m-1} & 0 < t \leq t^* \\ k\sigma^n & t > t^* \end{cases}. \quad (3)$$

Since creep rate at t^* should be continuous, which means

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c|_{(t^*-0)} = \dot{\varepsilon}_c|_{(t^*+0)}, \quad (4)$$

the creep rate can be given by:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c = \begin{cases} k\sigma^n t^{m-1}/t^{*m-1} & 0 < t \leq t^* \\ k\sigma^n & t > t^* \end{cases}. \quad (5)$$

Implementation of equivalence between creep and relaxation produces the following relationship:

$$\varepsilon_c + \varepsilon_e = \varepsilon = const, \quad (6)$$

where ε denotes the total strain, ε_c and ε_e represent the creep and elastic strain respectively. For ε_e is equal to σ/E where E represents the elasticity modulus, taking the derivative with respect to time on both sides further leads to

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_c = -\frac{1}{E} \frac{d\sigma}{dt} \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eq.(7) into Eq.(5) and forcing the variables to be identical on the left and right sides of the equation yield

$$\begin{cases} \left(\frac{t}{t^*}\right)^{m-1} dt = -\frac{1}{kE\sigma^n} d\sigma & 0 < t < t^* \\ dt = -\frac{1}{kE\sigma^n} d\sigma & t > t^* \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Integrating Eq.(8) under the assumption of $\sigma=\sigma_0$ at initial time ($t=t_0$) and forcing the left side of equation to be the ratio σ of to σ_0 yield

$$\frac{P_t}{P_0} = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} = \begin{cases} \left[1 + \frac{kE(n-1)\sigma_0^{n-1}t^m}{mt^{*m-1}}\right]^{-\frac{1}{n-1}} & 0 < t < t^* \\ \left[1 + kE(n-1)\sigma_0^{n-1}\left(\frac{t^*}{m} + t - t^*\right)\right]^{-\frac{1}{n-1}} & t > t^* \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Assumed $A = \frac{kE(n-1)\sigma_0^{n-1}}{mt^{*m-1}}$, $B = m$ and $C = -\frac{1}{n-1}$, one yields

$$\frac{P_t}{P_0} = \begin{cases} (1 + At^B)^C & 0 < t < t^* \\ [1 + A(1-B)t^{*B} + ABt^{*B-1}t]^C & t > t^* \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, Eq.(10) is generalized to account for the effects of temperature by using the temperature shift factors α_T . The time-dependent creep rate for a given temperature condition is then expressed as

$$\frac{P_t}{P_0} = \begin{cases} (1 + A(t/\alpha_T)^B)^C & 0 < t < t^* \\ [D + AB(t^*/\alpha_T)^{B-1}(t/\alpha_T)]^C & t > t^* \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Considering that $D = 1 + A(1-B)(t^*/\alpha_T)^B$ can be evaluated by other parameters, there are 5 independent parameters in Eq.(11). A, B and C are material constants, t^* is the critical time and α_T is the time-temperature shift factor. As shown in Eq.(11), the stress relaxation at the first stage is corresponding to the transient creep while second stage is corresponding to the steady stage.

All the parameters of Eq.(11) can be evaluated using least-squares regression analysis of short-term relaxation tests data. It should be noted that α_T can also be obtained by constructing master curve introduced in Section 3, it turned out that these two methods are able to determine almost the same shift factors.

Fig.3 Test setup

2.2 Parameters determination

For determining the parameters of the analyzed model, bolted relaxation experimental program was conducted. Eight specimens were tested during the tests. Different testing conditions are combined in Table 1. The four temperature conditions considered were 25°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C. Joint types included composite to composite joint and composite to metal hereinafter denoted by C-C and C-M joint, respectively. The torque 7 N·m is applied to produce the desired clamp-up force.

Each test coupon was a plate-like component with a dimension of 40×40×4mm. Both composite and metal materials were selected as the connection member of bolted joints. A schematic illustration of the experimental set-up is displayed in Figure 3. The joint assembly consisted of the composite test coupon, washer, hexagonal head steel bolt and copper sleeves. The hygrothermal chamber was used to control the experimental temperature. The data acquisition system is composed of a strain gauge pasted on the copper sleeve and a strain indicator working with frequency 1 Hz for monitoring strain data continuously during the test. Each test was repeated at least three times in order to average and obtain enough credible data. In all tests, the influence of humidity was not concerned so the humidity was set zero.

Joint Type	Initial preload/ N·m	Temperature/°C			
		25	50	70	90
C-C	7	CC-7-25	CC-7-50	CC-7-70	CC-7-90
C-M		CM-7-25	CM-7-50	CM-7-70	CM-7-90

Table 1 Conditions of the bolted relaxation test

After the hygrothermal chamber was preheated up to a setting experimental temperature, two interconnecting components were assembled with a bolt and clamped up to the desired torque. The initial strain of bolt was recorded as soon as torqued and the changing behavior of residual strain was monitored then. The whole test lasted for 36 hours. It is noteworthy that a specimen with non-preload was chosen as the baseline test configuration to counteract the eccentricity of temperature fluctuation. Each test was repeated at least three times in order to average and obtain enough credible data. The relaxation curves were showed in Figure 4 and 5 for C-C and C-M joints respectively.

The bolt relaxation at time t^* is denoted as the point where the relaxation rate stops decreasing and starts to keep stable. Provided that t^* is proportional to the total creep time t_{all} , analysis of the short-term relaxation curves such as Figure 4 reveals the ratio is about 1/3, considering $t^* = 1/3t_{all}$. A, B and C are evaluated through the regression analysis in term of the short-term relaxation data at room temperature (25°C, $\alpha_T=1$) and then α_T at various temperatures are obtained by combining the

Joint Type	A	B	C
C-C	0.01813	0.41702	-0.8
C-M	0.0171	0.8744	-0.0811

Table 2 Obtained parameters using Eq.(11)

Joint Type	25°C	50°C	70°C	90°C
C-C (a)	1	0.2709	0.08604	0.03571
C-C (b)	1	0.222626	0.07817	0.03605
C-M (a)	1	0.16866	0.07319	0.03561
C-M (b)	1	0.22627	0.06994	0.0359

Table 3 Shift factors α_T obtained by fitting tests data (a) or constructing master curves (b) at different temperatures

obtained value of A, B, C and the Phase II relaxation data. The parameters values are listed in **Table 2** and **Table 3(a)**.

Implementation of the above parameters conducted the short-term predicted results and showed a good consistency with the actual testing results which proves the validity preliminarily in a short period.

Fig.4 Preload relaxation time-dependent curves for C-C Joint at different temperatures

Fig.5 Preload relaxation time-dependent curves for C-M Joint at different temperatures

3 VERIFICATION OF MODEL

The accelerated test methodology is used to characterizing long-term behavior by using short-term tests. Since creep strain grows faster at a higher temperature than the reference temperature, one can accelerate a test by running it at a higher temperature. According to the TTSP, the retardation times at temperature T are reduced by a factor α_T and creep is accelerated by a factor α_T . Therefore, the data obtained at higher temperature were shifted to lower temperature in order to predict the relaxation at lower temperature for times that exceed the time available to do the test [18]. This kind of transformation can be described as follows:

$$E(T, t) = E(T_0, \frac{t}{\alpha_T}) = \Lambda(T_0, \log t - \log \alpha_T) \quad (12)$$

Fig.6 Preload relaxation curves (a), and the master curve at 25°C (b) for C-C Joint

Fig.7 Preload relaxation curves for various temperatures (a), and the master curve (b) of C-M Joint

Fig.8 Temperature dependence of shift factors (C-C Joint)

The same relaxation curves as Figure 4 and 5 but with log-log plot is illustrated on the left of Figure 6 and 7. Then they were translated horizontally with respect to the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$, to form the smooth master curve shown on the right. The amount each curve was shifted represents the logarithm of the previously described shift factor. Naturally, for the reference temperature is zero. Consistent with the use of the shift factor thus far, a shift to the left represents a positive shift. The results in terms of different temperatures are shown in Table 3(b) which have been found applicable to the Arrhenius law through regression analysis. Quantitatively, the Arrhenius equations show the rules between $\log \alpha_T$ and temperature (in Kelvin degree) for C-C joint and C-M joint respectively as follows

$$\log \alpha_T = \frac{2457}{T} - 8.26, \quad (13)$$

$$\log \alpha_T = \frac{2454}{T} - 8.25. \quad (14)$$

As illustrated in Figure 8, the relationship between $\log \alpha_T$ and $1/T$ let it possible to work out the shift factors for any given temperature. Therefore, by constructing a CC-7-90 test for 140 hours and combining it with Eq. (8), the 4200-hour relaxation behavior at 25°C , the 886-hour at 50°C and the 226-hour at 70°C for C-C joint were calculated equivalently and respectively for C-C joint. By the same token, constructing a CM-7-90 test for 140 hours and combining it with Eq. (9) produced the 4230-hour relaxation behavior at 25°C , the 891-hour at 50°C and the 275-hour at 70°C of C-M joint for C-M joint equivalently and respectively.

Fig.9 Comparison of accelerated tests and relaxation prediction for C-C joint at different temperatures

Fig.10 Comparison of accelerated tests and relaxation prediction for C-M joint at different temperatures

For the verification, predicted results of the developed model and accelerate tests results are compared in **Figure 9 and 10**. The good agreement between both proves the validity and accuracy of the phenomenological model established in this paper.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study, a detailed theoretical and experimental investigation was performed to characterize the long-term bolted preload relaxation for both composite and metal joints. A new predicted model is developed with implementation of the creep total-strain theory and a good agreement with accelerated testing results reveals its accuracy and validation.

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